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Research Article

**COMMONNESS OF DEPRESSION AMONG STUDENTS
DURING MBBS STUDIES**¹Dr Maria Maqsood, ²Dr Rabia Imtiaz, ³Dr Ziaullah¹Mayo Hospital Lahore, ²Services Hospital Lahore, ³Medical Officer Kunar Provincial Hospital, Afghanistan.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Performance of a person is greatly affected by depression and anxiety. Particularly medical students get stressed out due to both of these during their study.

Objectives: To analyze the commonness of depression in students studying at MBBS level during different stages.

Subjects and Methods: The study was conducted randomly and expressively at Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur. A group of 200 students (half males and half females) were selected randomly ranging from 18 to 24 years of age. To analyze the students, depression and anxiety scale was used. Students with score greater or equal to 20 were declared depressed. Special questionnaires were designed to obtain details. SPSS software version 16.0 was used to calculate the obtained details.

Results: It was found that from 200 subjects, 53(26.50%) were students with depression and 147(73.50%) were not. Percentage of depression among students decreased from 1st to 2nd to 3rd year of study from 29.27% to 25.64% to 15.15% respectively. In 4th year it increased to 25.53% which then increased up to 35% in last year of MBBS.

Conclusion: Depression is very much common in medical students. Increase in stress during 1st 3 years can be due to emotional discomfort. It increased afterwards due to more study and responsibilities. With their academic burden expanded, most stress among students is found in last year of study when they think of their future just a few more steps away.

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INTRODUCTION:

Generally, depression and anxiety are not well explained medically [1]. Depression is found to be 4th largest disease globally which declares it as a serious health issue [2]. It is illness of body, mood and thoughts. It effects the sleeping, eating and thinking habits of a person [3]. Anxiety is an unclear, unhappy emotion due to any problem [4]. World Health Organization(WHO) declared depression as a psychological disorder, unhappiness, low appetite, guilty feelings and lack of concentration with loss of interests [5]. Developing countries have a percentage of 10% to 44% population with depression and anxiety [6]. Exact percentage of anxiety in Pakistan is unknown [7]. But it too has a large rate of both diseases [2]. A study revealed that Lahore had 53.40%, Karachi had 14%-35% [2,8], Quetta had 43.90% and tribal areas had 60% of women and 45% of men with depression [9].

A study showed that rate of depression and anxiety increased among private college students of Lahore [10] from 19.30% to 70% in Agha Khan University and Jinnah Medical College Karachi [11]. Two different studies recorded rates of 23% [12] and 60% depressed students in Zia-ud-Din Medical University, Karachi [13]. In Zimbabwe 64.5% medical students of 1st year were found depressed [14]. Yet another research revealed that only 20% individuals in three Sydney hostels were stressed out [15]. The purpose of this study is to find out depression rate in Quaid e

Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur and to determine most stressful level of MBBS study.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

This questionnaire based study was conducted at QAMC Bahawalpur from Dec 2008 to June 2009.200 students (100 males & females each) were selected randomly from a total of 1300 students. Those not willing to answer the Questionnaire were eliminated from the sample. A thoroughly designed and already tested Questionnaire of Agha Khan University Anxiety and Depression Scale(AKUADS) was used to perform test. Students with scoreless or equal to 19 were considered as normal and those with more than 19 were considered depressed.25 symptoms and signs of anxiety and depression were included in Questionnaire which were judged by the interviewee himself. Students filled and returned the question paper. Obtained data was analyzed using SPSS version 16.0. Only descriptive statistics was applied using none of the statistical tests.

RESULTS:

Table-I shows that from 200 participants half (100) were males and half were females (100). Almost equal representations (about 20% each) were made from 1st to final year of MBBS. Results showed that 26.50% participants were depressed and 73.50% were not. Surprisingly, male students were found to be more depressed (28%) as compared to female students (25%).

Table-I: Characteristics of The Participants

Characteristics	Percentage
Year wise selection of study subjects	
1 st year	20.50 %
2 nd year	19.50 %
3 rd year	16.50 %
4 th year	23.50 %
Final year	20 %
Depression distribution	
Participants with depression	26.50 %
Participants without depression	73.50 %
Sex wise distribution of Depression	
Males with depression	28%
Females with depression	25%

Figure-I here shows the participants at different levels of MBBS with or without signs of depression. Rate of depression decreased from 1st to 2nd to 3rd year of study from 29.27% to 25.64% to 15.15% respectively. After 3rd year, it gradually increased from 4th year to final year of MBBS from 25.53% to highest at 35%.

Figure-1: Participants with and without depression at different Levels of MBBS.**DISCUSSION:**

Anxiety and depression are ranked as 4th major health issue all over the world [2]. These can be used efficiently in analyzing the mentality and learning of a student [13]. In 1956, it was stated that emotional stability of a student can affect his performance both at personal and professional levels [13]. Things due to which students get stressed out most because of medical training included burden of too much work, tension of getting prepared for exams, seeking education, capability and attitude [16]. Another important factor was that rate of depression decreased continuously from 1st to 3rd year. This was because student became able to manage themselves with the help of student's support system [17]. It then again increased from 4th year to last year probably due to patient dealings and ward duties.

Students of other undergraduate programs were found with less stress rate [18]. This was maybe because the medical students have to manage both normal and medical training life [19,20,21]. It includes many stressful times from admission to graduation along with making difficult decisions and dissection of dead body [22]. Very low rate of stress was also recorded among medical students [23,24]. This study calculated 26.50% students with depression and anxiety [10,12,15]. Our study gave result opposite to another study which showed that stress rate increases in 1st 3 years of MBBS study [25]. Other studies held factors like hospital work, dealing much ill patients, patients 'deaths, much study and duty stress responsible of increased depression during last years of study. [26]. Another research showed that Western female

students were more depressed than males. [27] [28] This was because over reporting by females. Whereas our female students are less distressed (25%) as compared to male students (28%). This can be explained with the facts that female students are provided social protection due to our religious beliefs. Also because the lady doctors are preferred in our society. On the other hand, males are considered to be jobholders of the family. They have to seek a source of earning right after study. This thought makes them depressed during studies which is noted most in last year of study.

CONCLUSION:

Large number of medical students get stressed out during study. Initial, stress rate increases because of their emotional instability which then decreases gradually up to 3rd year., it increases with the increase of clinical and ward responsibilities. Having much educational burden, sentiments of watching future at the doorstep and its responsibilities make final year of MBBS study most stressful.

REFERENES:

1. Amarl GFD, Gomide LMDP, Batista MDP, et al. Depressive symptoms in medical students of Universidade Federal de Goias: a prevalence study. *Rev Psiquiatr RS*.2008;30(2):124-130.
2. Toews MD, Lockyer JM, Dobson DJ, Simpson E, Brownell AK, Brennis F et al. Analysis Of stress levels among medical students residents and graduate students at four Canadian Schools of medicine. *Acad Med*. Nov 1997;72(11):997-1002.

3. Enns MW, Cox BJ, Sareen J, Freeman P. Adaptive and maladaptive perfectionism in medical students: a longitudinal investigation. *Med Educ*. Nov 2001; 35(11):1034-42.
4. Henningen P, Zimmermann T, Sattel H. Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, Anxiety and Depression: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Psychosomatic Medicine*.
5. Muhammad Gadit AA, Mugford G. Prevalence of Depression among Households among Three Capitals Cities of Pakistan. Need to revise the mental health policy. *POLoSONE*2(2): E209
6. Retrieved from: http://www.who.int/mental_health/management/depression/definition/en/
7. Retrieved from: http://www.who.int/mental_health/management/depression/definition/en/
8. Retrieved from: http://www.who.int/mental_health/management/depression/definition/en/
9. Luni FK, Jawad A, Shahid N, Baig SSM. Prevalence of Depression and Anxiety in rural region of Pakistan. *Biogenic Amines*.2008;22(1-2) : Supple 31-38
10. Retrieved from: http://www.who.int/mental_health/management/depression/definition/en/
11. Khan H, Kalia S, Itrat A, et al. Prevalence and Demographics of anxiety disorders: a snapshot from a community health centres in Pakistan. *Annals of General Psychiatry*.2007;6:30
12. Husain N, Chaudhary IB, Afridi MA, Tomenson B and Creed F. Life Stress And Depression In Tribal Areas Of Pakistan. *BJ Psych*.2007;190;36-41
13. Rab F, Mamdou R, and Nasir S. Rates of depression and anxiety among female medical students in Pakistan. *EMHJ*.2008 Vol.14 No.1
14. Khan MS, Mahmood S, Badshah A, AAli SU and Jamal Y. Prevalence of Depression, Anxiety and their associated factors among medical students in Karachi, Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc*. Dec 2006;56(12):583-86
15. Khwaja AK, Kadir MM. Gender Differences and clustering pattern of behavioural risk factors for chronic non-communicable diseases: community based study from a developing country. *Chronic Illness*. September 2010;6:163-170.
16. Inam SNB, Saqib A, Alam E. Prevalence of Anxiety and Depression among medical students of Private University. *J Pak Med Assoc*.2003;53-44
17. Vaz RF, Mbajiorgu EF, Acuda SW. A Preliminary study of stress levels among first year medical students at University Of Zimbabwe. *Cent Afr J Med*. Sep 1998;44(9);214-9
18. Snowdown J, Mackintosh S. Depression and Dementia in three Sydney hostels. *Australasian Journal on Ageing*.2008..Dec;8(4):24-28
19. Radcliffe C and Lester H. Perceived Stress during undergraduate medical training: a qualitative study. *Med Edu*. Jan 2003;37(1):32-8
20. Abdulghani HM. Stress and Depression among medical students. A cross sectional study at medical college in Saudi Arabia. *Pak J Med Sci*. Jan-March 2008;24(1)12-17
21. Yiu V. Supporting the well being of medical students. *CMAJ* Mar 2005;172(7):889-90
22. Miller GD, Miller EC, Peck OC. Medical Students need assessment and student affairs programming. *J Med Educ*.1981;56:518-20.
23. Firth J. Levels and sources of stress in medical students. *BMJ*.1986;292:1177-80
24. Supe AN. A study of stress in medical students at Seth G.S. Medical College. *J Postgrad Med*.1998;44:1-6.
25. Roscal OC, Ockene IS, Ockene JK, Barrett SV, Ma Y, and Hebert JR. A longitudinal study of students' depression at one medical school. *Journal of the Association of American Medical Colleges*. 1997.72.6.
26. Helmers KF, Danoff D, Steinert Y, Young SN, Stressed and depressed mood in medical students, law students and graduate students at McGill University. *Acad Med*. 1997;72(8):708-14
27. Verbuegge LM. Gender And Health: an update on hypothesis and evidence. *J Health Soc Behav*. Sep 1985;26(3):156-82
28. Goldin SB, Wahi MM, Farooq AS, et al. Student Quality of Life Declines during Third Year Surgical Clerkship. *Journal Of Surgical Research*. Nov 2007;143(1):151-157.